

Spectrophotometric Study of the Picric Acid-Copper Ammoniate Complex

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Ammoniacal solution of copper sulphate with picric acid forms an olive-green precipitate. Spectrophotometric study of the decanted supernatant liquid reveals the composition of the complex as 1:2 of Cu (II) to picric acid in case of solutions of picric acid of concentrations $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ and of copper salt of the same concentration or more.

Bobtelsky and Kertes¹ studied spectrophotometrically the complex formation of picric acid, 2,4-dinitrophenol, and *p*-nitrophenol with Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , and Co^{2+} salts. They concluded the nitro group, *ortho* to OH, to be essential for complex formation and that complex formation was independent of acid strength. Korenman² showed that picric acid in ammoniacal solution produced a bright greenish precipitate with copper sulphate solution, etc. Agafoshin³ studied complex compounds of picric acid and some other nitrophenols with copper ammoniate solution.

In the present investigation, complex formation by picric acid with ammoniacal copper sulphate solution has been studied by use of 'Uvispek' spectrophotometer. An aqueous solution of picric acid, when added to an ammoniacal solution of $Cu(OH)_2$, produces the precipitate of $[C_6H_3(NO_2)_3O]_2 Cu(NH_3)_4$.

In the complex formation between copper salt and picric acid, the previous workers found the complex formed in solution, whereas by using ammoniacal copper sulphate solution, the present authors found the complex formed as an insoluble precipitate, thus:

The maximum precipitation would occur when the two components, A and B, are in the stoichiometric ratio. For picric acid solution, absorbance becomes less with increasing wave length and for ammoniacal copper sulphate solutions this increases with increasing wave length. Hence the absorbance of radiation by the supernatant liquid gives a peak by plotting the difference in absorbance against the volume of one of the components, using Job's method⁴ of continued variation. Here the absorbance difference, unlike in the complex formed remaining in solution, of the mixture minus the sum of absorbances due to the two constituents is negative. The peak is obtained when this negative value of the difference in absorbance ($-\Delta D$) is plotted against volume of one of the constituents in ml, viz., the ammoniacal copper sulphate solution. The ratio of the two constituents

1. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1955, 22, 328.

2. *Chem. Abs.*, 1931, 25, 2938.

3. *J. Gen. Chem., U.S.S.R.*, 1937, 7, 2235.

4. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.

at the peak, thus provides a means of determining the ratio in which they are used in forming the complex.

The results of investigations for solutions of picric acid and copper salt of different concentrations are summarised below:

(i) By using concentrations of $M/100$ picric acid and $M/200$ ammoniacal copper sulphate no conclusive results are obtained, nor for solutions of lesser concentrations than these.

(ii) Using concentrations ranging between $M/100$ and $M/40$ of each of the picric acid and of the copper salt, definite conclusions are derived.

(iii) As ammonia enters in the complex, the smaller amount of it produces erratic results because of the possible hydrolysis of the complex formed. It has therefore to be added in excess.

The suitable wave lengths were found by measuring absorbance due to ammoniacal copper sulphate and picric acid solutions separately and then due to a mixture of the two, within 230 to 600 $m\mu$. For $M/100$ picric acid solution, suitable wave lengths are 470, 480, and 490 $m\mu$ and when $M/40$ picric acid is used, the wave lengths are 480, 490, and 500 $m\mu$. For wave lengths 470 $m\mu$ or lower in more concentrated solutions of picric acid, the absorbance becomes unmeasurable. Within these wave lengths absorbance due to ammoniacal copper sulphate solutions is quite significant.

The results for mixtures prepared by the continued variation method are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Fig. 1 includes graphs for equimolar solutions and Fig. 2, non-equimolar solutions. Total amount of the mixture in each case was made 10ml. The amount of ammoniacal copper sulphate present in the mixture was plotted against difference in absorbance (ΔD), as shown by:

$$\Delta D = D_M - (D_P + D_{Cu})$$

where D_M is absorbance due to the mixture, D_P due to picric acid, and D_{Cu} to ammoniacal copper sulphate solution of the requisite strength present in the mixture.

TABLE I

Curve.	Wave length.	Picric acid.	Cu-ammoniate.	Peak at x ml of $CuSO_4$ soln.
A. Equimolar soln. (Fig. 1).				
a	470 $m\mu$	$1 \times 10^{-2} M$	1×10^{-2}	3.3
b	480	"	"	"
c	490	"	"	"
d	480	2.5×10^{-2}	2.5×10^{-2}	"
e	490	"	"	"
f	500	"	"	"
B. Non-equimolar soln. (Fig. 2).				
a	480	2×10^{-2}	1×10^{-2}	5.0
b	480	"	"	"
c	500	"	"	"
d	480	2.5×10^{-2}	1.25×10^{-2}	"
e	490	"	"	"
f	500	"	"	"

These results conclusively show that this continued variation method, spectrophotometrically studied, confirms the contention that the complex of picric acid and ammoniacal copper sulphate has the composition of 2 parts of the acid to one of salt.

The monovariation method followed by Nayar and Pandey⁵ provides results in agreement with those obtained by the continued variation method.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

EXPERIMENTAL

Pure picric acid (B.D.H.), further purified and dried, and 'Analar' (B.D.H.) copper sulphate were used in the preparation of the solutions. The distilled water was re-distilled in silica vessels. Stock solutions of concentrations $M/40$ each of picric acid and copper sulphate were prepared and other solutions were obtained from it by dilution. To copper sulphate solution liquor ammonia was added in excess before making to the mark. Solutions were mixed by use of micro-burettes in well-stoppered bottles to obtain

the required mixture. The precipitate formed was allowed to settle for 1 hour, the supernatant liquid decanted, and its absorbance was measured. During the time of a set of observations, carried in an inner room, temperature variations were less than $\pm 3^\circ$. Hilger 'Uvispek' spectrophotometer was used for measuring the absorbance. Further work conductometrically and with other metals, Ni and Ag, is in progress.

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